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8 **Nontargeted Mass Spectrometry of Dried Blood Spots for**
9 **Interrogation of the Human Circulating Metabolome**
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1 **ABSTRACT**

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3 Advances in high resolution, nontargeted mass spectrometry allow for the simultaneous measure of
4 thousands of metabolites in a single biosample. Application of these analytical approaches to
5 population-scale human studies has been limited by the need for resource-intensive blood sample
6 collection, preparation, and storage. Dried blood spotting, a technique developed decades ago for
7 newborn screening, may offer a simple approach to overcome barriers in human blood acquisition and
8 storage. In this study, we find that over 4,400 spectral features across diverse chemical classes may
9 be efficiently and reproducibly extracted and relatively quantified from human dried blood spots using
10 nontargeted metabolomic analysis employing reversed-phase liquid chromatography coupled to
11 Orbitrap mass spectrometry. Moreover, over 80% of metabolites were found to be chemically stable in
12 dried blood spots stored at room temperature for up to a week. In direct relation to plasma samples,
13 dried blood spots exhibited comparable representation of the human circulating metabolome, capturing
14 both known and previously uncharacterized metabolites. Dried blood spot approaches provide an
15 opportunity for rapid and facile human biosampling and storage, and will enable widespread
16 metabolomics study of populations, particularly in resource-limited areas.

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1 INTRODUCTION

2 The measurement and characterization of circulating metabolites holds enormous potential to advance
3 and transform our understanding of human biology, providing deep insight into disease pathogenesis,
4 drug responsiveness, and dynamic environmental exposures such as diet.^{1,2} Advances in high-
5 throughput chromatography and high-resolution mass spectrometry have facilitated the measurement
6 of thousands of metabolites within a single biosample,^{3,4} the majority of which remain structurally and
7 functionally uncharacterized.⁵ Coupled software and computational advances have made it possible to
8 improve the scale of experiments,⁶⁻¹⁰ a shift that will undoubtedly lead to better characterization of
9 human chemical diversity, interactions among environmental influences and genetic factors, and
10 ultimately personalization of dietary and pharmaceutical therapies.

11 These analytical and technical advances have prompted a renewed focus on optimization and
12 streamlining of patient sample acquisition, storage, and processing, particularly for population-scale
13 studies on the order of 10,000 to 1,000,000 biosamples. Traditional approaches are both labor and
14 cost intensive, requiring trained health professionals, access to specialized equipment such as
15 centrifuges, as well as immediate cold storage and refrigerated transport in specialized containers.^{11,12}
16 These barriers to sample acquisition are particularly constraining in studies involving children and
17 individuals residing in resource-poor areas.^{13,14} Dried blood spotting, a method developed nearly 60
18 years ago for blood biosampling, may represent a scalable and cost-effective solution for human blood
19 acquisition and storage, particularly for metabolomics studies.

20 Dried blood spots (DBS) are currently widely employed for sampling of blood from newborns for
21 neonatal screening. Typically, several drops of blood (~50 μ L per spot) are collected from a peripheral
22 prick from newborns and spotted on a Guthrie card. Using these samples, multiple targeted metabolites
23 are routinely assayed to identify inborn errors of metabolism or drug levels in select cases.¹⁵ Recent
24 studies suggest that a broader range of metabolites may be potentially assayed from DBS, beyond
25 those traditionally examined for neonatal screening.¹⁶⁻²⁰ For instance, prior studies have detailed the
26 measurement of heavy metals and pesticides from DBS, which reflect potential *in utero* exposures,^{21,22}
27 as well as a broad range of metabolites associated with birth weight.²³ To date, however, the application
28 of dried blood systems for nontargeted metabolomics analysis across thousands of metabolites is
29 limited. Prior investigations of nontargeted liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LCMS) of DBS
30 demonstrate reliable measure of a few hundred up to one thousand unique spectral features.²³⁻²⁵
31 However, the full chemical diversity of the human metabolites that may be extracted and assayed from
32 small volumes of blood stored as DBS, the relation of DBS to traditional venipuncture samples, the
33 impact of blood spot location, and the stability of metabolites in stored DBS, remain incompletely
34 characterized.

35 In this study, we perform a comprehensive characterization of DBS as biosample storage devices for
36 nontargeted reversed-phase LC- Orbitrap MS metabolomic studies. We present optimized sample
37 preparation approaches for extraction of different classes of metabolites from DBS, as well as determine
38 intra-spot variation of detectable analytes and stability of metabolites in DBS stored at room temperature
39 over time. To determine the impact of potential sample-matrix interactions on the fidelity of metabolite
40 measures from DBS, we perform nontargeted LCMS and of matched DBS and plasma samples.

41 42 MATERIALS AND METHODS

43
44 **Chemicals and Consumables.** Whatman 903 Protein Saver Cards (GE healthcare) were used for all
45 DBS experiments. LC-MS grade reagents were purchased from Honeywell (Methanol, Isopropyl
46 Alcohol, Ammonium Bicarbonate and Acetic Acid), Fisher (water and Ammonium Hydroxide), and
47 Sigma Aldrich (Acetonitrile and Ethanol). Well plates were purchased from Greiner Bio-One (96 well 1
48 mL Master Block plates) and Axygen (96-well V-bottom 600 μ L).

49
50 **Blood Samples.** Pooled whole blood collected via venipuncture were obtained from BioIVT. All BioIVT
51 whole blood samples (which were collected in EDTA tubes) were stored at 4 °C prior to use and were
52 spotted prior to stated expiration date. DBS cards spotted with blood collected via venipuncture
53 containing known concentrations for 29 metabolites from diverse chemical classes were obtained from

1 the CDC (Newborn Screening Quality Assurance Program) and used for dynamic range of
2 concentration and linearity of dilution experiments. CDC dried blood spot samples were stored at -20
3 °C in accordance with CDC recommendations and were used prior to stated expiration date.

4
5 **Optimization of extraction of metabolites from DBS.** DBS samples were prepared by spotting 50 µL
6 of whole blood in the center of the demarcated area of a Whatman 903 card via single channel pipette,
7 which allowed for five 3 mm punches to be taken per spot with one central and four peripheral locations
8 (Figure 1C). Spotted cards were then placed horizontally on a Whatman 903 card rack. The rack was
9 placed in a Styrofoam container with *Drierite* desiccant chips and allowed to dry over 3.5 hours. Once
10 dehydrated, cards were folded and placed in a freezer grade plastic bag with a silica gel desiccator
11 pouch and a O₂ absorbent packet. Finally, bags were placed in a covered box to avoid light exposure
12 and stored at -80 °C. All spots were analyzed within a month of spotting. Plasma was prepared by
13 spinning whole blood at 5300 rpm (~2,000 g) for 15 minutes at 4 °C and then transferring 500 µL of
14 plasma supernatant to a fresh microfuge tube.

15
16 For metabolite extraction, a 3 mm diameter punch from each blood spot (n=3 for each optimization
17 condition) was deposited into separate wells of a Greiner Master Block 1 mL 96 well plate, which was
18 kept on ice. Blank Whatman 903 paper was punched two times after each spot was taken to prevent
19 carry-over between samples. To optimize the amount of water needed to initially hydrate the blood
20 spots, various amounts of water were added to each well (100 µL, 80 µL, 60 µL, 40 µL, or 20 µL), sealed
21 and then placed on an orbital shaker for agitation at 2000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4 °C. Various amounts
22 of organic solvent (ethanol [EtOH], methanol [MeOH], acetonitrile [ACN], or 1:1 methanol/acetonitrile
23 [MeOH:ACN]) were then added to each well (100 µL, 120 µL, 140 µL, 160 µL, or 180 µL, respective to
24 the water volumes so each well contained 200 µL total volume). The plate was re-sealed and agitated
25 again at 2000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C. After shaking, the plate was centrifuged at 4200 rpm for 10
26 minutes at 4 °C. Varying volumes of supernatant were then transferred to a fresh 1 mL 96 well plate
27 with 200 µL glass inserts and diluted with water 1:3, 1:2, and 1:1 with 40:40:20 MeOH:ACN:H₂O for
28 polar metabolites and 35:35:30 MeOH:ACN:H₂O for lipid analysis or was not diluted with water at all.
29 For the “2x” concentration tests, 100 µL of supernatant was dried in a speed vac at 40°C for ~1 hour
30 and then re-constituted in 50 µL of a solution of 40:40:20 MeOH:ACN:H₂O for the polar metabolites and
31 35:35:30 MeOH:ACN:H₂O for lipid analysis. The reconstitution step involved 10 minutes of orbital
32 shaking at 650 RPM. Water hydration and organic solvent shake times were also optimized (1, 5, 10,
33 15, 20, and 30 minutes). For the Bioactives method, supernatant dilution was not tested but rather the
34 amount of supernatant loaded onto the solid phase extraction (SPE) plate was evaluated (25 µL, 50 µL,
35 75 µL, 100 µL, 125 µL, or 150 µL).

36 37 **Optimized metabolite extraction protocols.**

38 *Polar Metabolite Extraction.* After placing the 3 mm DBS punch into a 1 mL 96 well plate, 40 µL of water
39 was transferred into the well and agitated via orbital shaking for 10 minutes at 2000 RPM. After shaking,
40 160 µL of ACN:MeOH (1:1) was added to the wells, and the plate was agitated again for 10 minutes at
41 2000 RPM. The plate was then centrifuged at 4200 RPM at 4 °C for 10 minutes. After shaking, 100 µL
42 of supernatant was transferred into an Axygen V-bottom plate and placed in a vacuum concentrator
43 until samples were dry. The solution was then re-constituted in 50 µL of ACN:MeOH:H₂O solution
44 (40:40:20) and shaken again in an orbital shaker at 650 RPM for 10 minutes. Then, 50 µL of supernatant
45 was transferred to a 1 mL 96 well plate with glass inserts, and centrifuged at 4200 RPM at 4 °C for 10
46 minutes. Supernatant was then analyzed by LC-MS.

47
48 *Bioactive Metabolite Extraction.* After placing the 3 mm DBS punch into a 1 mL 96 well plate, 40 µL of
49 water was transferred into the well and agitated via orbital shaking for 10 minutes at 2000 RPM. After
50 shaking, 160 µL of EtOH was added to each well and the plate was again shaken for 10 minutes at
51 2000 RPM. The plate was then centrifuged at 4200 RPM at 4 °C for 10 minutes. Then, 150 µL of
52 supernatant was loaded onto a Phenomenex Strata-X SPE plate and metabolites were extracted
53 according to previously reported protocols.²⁶

54

1 *Lipid Metabolite Extraction.* After placing the 3 mm DBS punch into a 1 mL 96 well plate, 60 μ L of water
2 was transferred into the well and agitated via orbital shaking for 10 minutes at 2000 RPM. After shaking,
3 140 μ L of ACN:MeOH (1:1) was added to the wells, and the plate was again shaken for 10 minutes at
4 2000 RPM. The plate was then centrifuged at 4200 RPM at 4 °C for 10 minutes after which 100 μ L of
5 supernatant was transferred into an Axygen V-bottom plate and placed in a vacuum concentrator until
6 samples were dry. The solution was then re-constituted in 50 μ L of ACN:MeOH:H₂O solution (35:35:30)
7 and shaken again in an orbital shaker at 650 RPM for 10 minutes. Then, 50 μ L of supernatant was
8 transferred to a fresh 1 mL 96 well plate containing 200 μ L glass inserts, centrifuged at 500 RPM for 10
9 minutes, and then analyzed by LC-MS.

10
11 **Quality Control Protocols.** An instrument solvent blank was determined by analyzing the 2 solvents
12 used for the extraction protocols above, MeOH:ACN and EtOH, prior to LC-MS analysis of samples. In
13 addition, the supernatants from blank, unspotted Whatman cards subjected to extraction with
14 MeOH:ACN and EtOH separately were analyzed by LC-MS to determine contaminant spectral peaks
15 related to the Whatman cards. Spectral peaks related to solvents or Whatman cards were subtracted
16 from sample LC-MS data. A method blank was also analyzed to account for any laboratory background.
17 Samples were analyzed in a randomized fashion and were interspaced with injections of a QC standard
18 (¹³C glutamine for Polar method; 1-cyclohexyl-dodecanoic acid urea [CUDA] for Lipids method,
19 and a mix of the following for the Bioactives method: 9-HODE; 13-HODE; 9,10-diHOME; 12,13-
20 diHOME; 15-deoxy-d12,14-PGJ2; 5-oxoETE; 20-HETE; 15-HETE; 12-HETE; 5S-HETE; LTB4; CUDA;
21 13,14-dihydro-15-keto-PGD2; PGE2; PGE2; PGD2; 13,14-dihydro-15-keto-PGF2a; PGF2a/6-keto-
22 PGF1a/TXB2/Resolvin D1). The QC sample was measured after every 20 sample injections.

23 24 **LC-MS methods**

25 *Polar metabolites:* Polar metabolites: Once prepared, 2 μ l of sample was injected onto a SeQuant Zic-
26 pHILIC (5 μ m particle size, 100 x 2.1 mm) column and separated using mobile phases A (20 mM
27 Ammonium Bicarbonate in water with pH 9.6) and B (100% Acetonitrile) running the following gradient:
28 90% B from 0 to 0.25 min, 90% to 55% B from 0.250 to 4 min, and 55% B from 4 min to 6 min, followed
29 by a 2.5-minute re-equilibration time. The flow rate was set at 0.4 mL/min and the column compartment
30 temperature at 45 °C. Mass detection was performed using a Thermo QExactive orbitrap mass
31 spectrometer equipped with a heated electrospray ionization (HESI) source and collision-induced
32 dissociation (CID) fragmentation. The source settings used for all samples were: negative and positive
33 ion mode profile data, sheath gas flow of 40 units, aux gas flow of 15 units, sweep gas flow of 2 units,
34 spray voltage of +/- 3.5kV, capillary temperature of 275 °C, aux gas temp of 350 °C, S-lens RF at 45.
35 For MS1 scan events, scan ranges were set to m/z 65-975, mass resolution of 35k, AGC of 1e6 and
36 injection time of 75 ms was used. For tandem MS acquisition, mass resolution of 17.5k, AGC of 1e5
37 and injection time of 50 ms was used.

38
39 *Bioactive metabolites:* Once prepared, 20 μ l of sample was injected onto a Phenomenex Kinetex C18
40 (1.7 μ m particle size, 100 x 2.1 mm) column that was pre-conditioned with plasma and separated using
41 mobile phases A (70% water, 30% acetonitrile, 0.1% acetic acid) and B (50% acetonitrile, 50% isopropyl
42 alcohol, 0.2% acetic acid) running the following gradient: 1% B from 0 to 0.25 min, 1% to 55% B from
43 0.25 to 5 min, 55% to 99% B from 5.0 to 5.5 min, 99% B from 5.5 min to 7 min, followed by a 1 min re-
44 equilibration time. The flow rate was set at 0.375 mL/min and the column compartment temperature at
45 50 °C. Mass detection was performed using a Thermo QExactive orbitrap mass spectrometer equipped
46 with a heated electrospray ionization (HESI) source and collision-induced dissociation (CID)
47 fragmentation. The source settings used for all samples were: negative ion mode profile data, sheath
48 gas flow of 40 units, aux gas flow of 10 units, sweep gas flow of 2 units, spray voltage of -3.55kV,
49 capillary temperature of 265 °C, aux gas temp of 350 °C, S-lens RF at 45. For MS1 scan events, scan
50 ranges were set to 225-650 m/z, mass resolution of 17.5k, AGC of 1e5 and injection time of 50 ms was
51 used. For tandem MS acquisition, mass resolution of 17.5k, AGC of 1e5 and injection time of 50 ms
52 was used.

53
54 *Lipid metabolites:* Once prepared, 10 μ l of sample was injected onto an Agilent EclipsePlus C18 (1.8
55 μ m particle size, 2.1 x 50 mm) column and separated using mobile phases A (0.2% acetic acid in water)

1 and B (50% acetonitrile, 50% isopropyl alcohol, 0.2% acetic acid) running the following gradient: 5% B
2 from 0 to 0.5 min, 5% to 40% B from 0.5 to 3 min, 40% to 80% B from 3 to 9.5 min, 80% to 100% from
3 9.5 to 11 min, and 100% B from 11min to 13 min, followed by a 2 minute re-equilibration time. The flow
4 rate was set at 0.5 mL/min and the column compartment temperature at 50 °C. Mass detection was
5 performed using a Thermo QExactive orbitrap mass spectrometer equipped with a heated electrospray
6 ionization (HESI) source and collision-induced dissociation (CID) fragmentation. The source settings
7 used for all samples were: negative and positive ion mode profile data, sheath gas flow of 40 units, aux
8 gas flow of 10 units, sweep gas flow of 2 units, spray voltage of +/- 3.55kV, capillary temperature of 265
9 °C, aux gas temp of 350 °C, S-lens RF at 45. For MS1 scan events, scan ranges were set to 120-1800
10 m/z, mass resolution of 60k, AGC of 1e6 and injection time of 100ms was used. For tandem MS
11 acquisition, mass resolution of 15k, AGC of 2e5 and injection time of 50 ms was used.

12
13 **Metabolite Identification and Chemical Networking.** Identification of known signals was performed
14 using commercial standards and comparison of MS/MS spectra to reference spectra. First, accurate
15 mass (within 10 ppm), retention time (within 0.1 minute) and MS/MS fragmentation pattern were
16 searched against reference data from an in-house library of 852 commercial standards. Second, all
17 experimental MS/MS spectra were searched against public repositories of MS/MS data using the GNPS
18 Library Search function (<https://gnps.ucsd.edu>). Search tolerances included: Accurate Mass < 10ppm,
19 Minimum match score of 0.80, allowed adducts of [M+H, M+Na, M+NH₄, M+H-H₂O, M-H, M+Acetate,
20 M-H-H₂O]. All MS/MS matches were manually inspected and confirmed. In total, 333 compounds across
21 all 3 methods were positively identified. For generation of MS/MS networks, the GNPS Molecular
22 Networking function was used using the following parameters: MZ tolerance of 0.01 Da, Min Matched
23 Peaks of 6, Min Cosine Score of 0.7, TopK of 10, Max Cluster Size of 100, and MS Cluster size of 2.
24 For library matching, the following parameters were used: Min Cosine Score of 0.8, Min Matched peaks
25 of 6, and MS1 tolerance of <10ppm (manually trimmed post creation). Network was visualized using
26 Cytoscape version 3.7.2 (<https://cytoscape.org>).

27
28 **Evaluation of technical variance.** We determined relative standard deviation for measurements by
29 analyzing 16 samples (technical replicates) and one blank. Once re-suspended, 6 samples were pooled
30 via transfer to an Eppendorf tube. The pooled and non-pooled DBS supernatant were then run on the
31 LC-MS protocols described above. Dynamic concentration range and linearity of dilution experiments
32 were performed using quality control cards spotted with whole blood with known concentrations of
33 amino acids and acylcarnitines (Lots A1715, B1715, C1715, D1715) obtained from the CDC. Samples
34 were run in quintuplicate with one blank per concentration. Samples were then processed via the
35 methods described above and run on the LC-MS. The studies conducted to assess the impact of
36 location (central vs. peripheral) of blood spotting on metabolite detection and quantification were done
37 using pooled whole blood samples from one card that was punched 5 times from each of the 5 blood
38 spots (1 central and 4 peripheral locations) on the card. One blank was chosen for each of the 5 spot
39 locations. Samples were then processed via the respective optimized extraction methods outlined
40 above and analyzed using the LC-MS protocols described below.

41
42 **Assessment of Metabolite Stability in DBS at Room Temperature.** Whole blood DBS samples were
43 prepared as described above. All DBS cards were placed into separate Mylar storage bags with an
44 oxygen absorbent packet and desiccant bags. The first sample was designated as the day 0 and
45 immediately placed in an -80 °C freezer. The other samples were then stored at room temperature.
46 Every 24 hours, an additional Mylar bag with samples was placed in the -80 °C freezer over a 7-day
47 period. Metabolite stability DBS samples from day 0 to day 7 were then assessed by extracting
48 metabolites via methods above. Samples were taken in quintuplicate. For these assays, we only
49 selected MS spectral features that were not present in solvent and Whatman card blanks and were
50 detectable in over 80% of quintuplicate samples on Day 0.

51
52 **Comparison of Plasma Metabolite Analysis in DBS versus Plasma.** For comparison of DBS and
53 plasma measures, plasma samples were prepared according to the following protocols. For metabolite
54 extraction, 20 µL of plasma prepared from matched whole blood were added to 80 µL of organic solvent
55 (ethanol for the Bioactives method and 1:1 ACN:MeOH for the Polar metabolites and Lipids protocols)

1 and mixed in an orbital shaker at 2000 RPM for 10 minutes. Samples were then centrifuged at 4200
2 RPM at 4 °C for 10 minutes. For Polar metabolite and Lipids methods, 50 μ L of supernatant was
3 transferred to a 1 mL 96 well plate containing 200 μ L glass inserts and analyzed by LC-MS. For the
4 Bioactives method, samples were prepared as previously described.²⁶

5
6 **Data handling and analysis.** For data processing, in-house R-scripts were used to perform initial bulk
7 feature alignment, MS1-MS2 data parsing, pseudo DIA-to-DDA MS2 deconvolution, and CSV-to-MGF
8 file generation. RAW to mzXML file conversion was performed using MSconvert version 3.0.9393 (part
9 of the ProteoWizard Software Suite). Feature extraction, secondary alignment, and compound
10 identification were performed using both mzMine 2.21 as well as Progenesis QI software suites.
11 Statistical analysis was performed using R (3.3.3).

12 13 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

14 **Optimization and Validation of Metabolomics Approaches for Dried Blood Spots** Currently,
15 optimized protocols for metabolomics analysis of specific chemical classes of small molecules in DBS
16 are not well established. We therefore developed operating workflows that allow for facile extraction
17 and analysis of diverse metabolites from DBS, followed by nontargeted LCMS-based metabolomics
18 using an Orbitrap mass analyzer. After spotting 50 μ L of blood on a Whatman 903 card, metabolites
19 are extracted from a 3 mm punches taken from the DBS and analyzed by reversed-phase LC- Orbitrap
20 MS (**Figure 1A**, Methods). In order to capture the widest possible range of metabolic information from
21 DBS, three independent LC-MS methods were developed for measuring polar small molecules (Polar
22 method), polar bioactive lipids (Bioactives method), and large nonpolar lipids (Lipids method). For each
23 method, metabolite extraction conditions were optimized around the following parameters: choice of
24 organic solvent (methanol, acetonitrile, ethanol, methanol:acetonitrile [MeOH:ACN]), organic solvent-
25 dilution, and final sample/supernatant concentration. For all methods, acetonitrile showed the lowest
26 number of total features owing to its limited solubility profile. Acetonitrile was also prone to cause
27 clogging during liquid handling due to its adhesive precipitate. Methanol and 1:1 MeOH:ACN performed
28 well across all methods, with MeOH:ACN showing best overall performance in the Polar and Lipids
29 methods when reproducibility across multiple extractions, as well as the total number of peaks extracted
30 and average peak intensity, were considered (**Figure 1B**, left panel-Polar method; **Suppl Figure 1B**,
31 left panel – Bioactives method). Ethanol performed particularly well in the Bioactives method (**Suppl**
32 **Figure 1A**, left panel) across all criteria, and while it did produce a high number of abundant peaks in
33 the Polar method, it also had the highest degree of instability from replicate extractions. For organic
34 solvent to water ratio, 70% organic solvent performed most efficiently for the Lipid method (**Suppl Figure**
35 **1B**, middle panel), while 80% organic solvent was optimal for the Polar (**Figure 1B**, middle panel) and
36 Bioactive (**Suppl Figure 1B**, middle panel). Lastly, all methods favored high sample concentrations
37 with Polar and Lipids methods performing best when the supernatant was concentrated two-fold (**Figure**
38 **1B**, right panel; **Suppl Figure 1B**, right panel) and with the Bioactives method performing best with
39 150 μ L SPE loading (**Suppl Figure 1A**, right panel). Collectively, these three LC-MS approaches
40 resulted in capture of over 4,400 spectral features from DBS samples. From these spectral features,
41 333 metabolites were positively identified using commercial standards and matching of experimental
42 MS/MS spectra against reference libraries (**Suppl Table 1**). Identified metabolites include those related
43 to a number of metabolic diseases, such as phenylketonuria, hyperarginemia, tyrosinemia, lysosomal
44 storage disorders, disorders of fatty acid oxidations, carnitine transport deficiencies, and ornithine
45 transcarbamylase deficiency, among others. In addition, we observed many endogenous metabolites
46 involved in energetic balance including metabolites within the TCA cycle, pyruvic acid pathway, vitamin
47 metabolism, fat oxidation, nicotinamide/NAD, and phosphorylated moieties. Metabolites related to
48 environmental exposures, including pesticides, drugs, diet and medications, were also measured in
49 DBS, several of which have been previously assayed using DBS samples.²⁰

50 Typically, blood spotting is performed by placement of several drops of whole blood on the center of a
51 DBS paper, with passive diffusion of the biosample through the paper matrix. As such, we next
52 determined whether physical location in relation to the point of spotting influenced metabolite
53 measurement. When peripheral and central blood spot locations were analyzed (**Figure 1C**), we found
54 that only 36 of 4,405 spectral features (~ 1%) demonstrated greater than two-fold change according to

1 location on the DBS (**Figure 1C, Venn diagram**), which was consistent across chemical classes (**Suppl**
2 **Figure 1C**). Interestingly, among those molecules that were found to change significantly with physical
3 location across the DBS were flavonoids, a class of plant-derived polyphenolic molecules,²⁷ which were
4 consistently found to be higher in the DBS periphery relative to center. While the vast majority of
5 metabolites were highly stable across the DBS, these findings suggest a matrix-analyte interaction may
6 promote variable physical migration for a small subset of metabolites.

7
8 To determine the robustness of metabolite measures using DBS, technical replication was evaluated.
9 Across 48 blood replicates, over 80% of assayed metabolites, totaling over 3,500 individual features,
10 exhibited a relative standard deviation (RSD) of <20% with an overall median RSD of 11.2% (**Figure**
11 **1D**), comparable to prior nontargeted LC-MS analysis of human plasma.²⁸ RSD was related to
12 metabolite intensity, with lower intensity features closer to the signal-to-noise threshold exhibiting
13 greater technical variance, as expected (**Figure 1D**). To determine the relative contribution of metabolite
14 extraction from individual DBS handling vs. LC-MS measure to the total technical variance, extracted
15 metabolites from individual technical replicates were pooled together, mixed, and subjected to repeated
16 measure. Across all metabolites, the difference in RSD between pooled and non-pooled samples was
17 between 1-6% (data not shown), suggesting that DBS handling and metabolite extraction contribute
18 only minimally to total technical variance.

19 We next evaluated the relative quantitation and dynamic linear range for metabolites measured from
20 DBS using Center for Disease Control (CDC) DBS cards spotted with blood containing known
21 concentrations for 28 metabolites typically assayed for newborn screening.^{29,30} Relative measure of
22 these metabolites showed excellent linearity across physiologic and pathologic concentration ranges,
23 irrespective of chemical class, with R² values greater than 0.95 (**Figure 1E, Table 1**). Collectively, these
24 results highlight optimized approaches for robust, nontargeted mass spectrometry-based metabolomic
25 measurements of thousands of circulating human metabolites from DBS biosamples.

26 27 **Stability of Metabolites in DBS at Room Temperature**

28 Dried blood spotting functions through rapid desiccation of samples with suspension of enzymatic
29 reactions that may lead to the breakdown of metabolites,³¹ enabling potential short-term storage at room
30 temperature (RT) prior to analysis. Prior investigation of rodent blood spots showed limited stability of
31 metabolites with storage at RT after 1-4 weeks.³² Similar observations have been made in studies of
32 human newborn DBS¹⁸ and adult whole blood DBS³³ over periods of time ranging from 1 week up to 2
33 years after blood spotting; however, a detailed, high-resolution temporal profile of metabolite stability
34 over the first week after blood spotting does not exist to date. Given that one week represents a period
35 of time that would theoretically allow for point of care sampling and transport from most worldwide
36 locations to central facilities for cold storage and analysis, we investigated the stability of blood
37 metabolites in DBS at RT over the first 7 days after spotting. Metabolomic analysis revealed that across
38 the week-long period at RT, less than 20% of the ~4,400 spectral features assayed changed more than
39 2-fold (**Figure 2**). Interestingly, among those metabolites found to be altered by RT storage over the 7-
40 day period, significant change in relative concentration was observed primarily during the first 24 hours,
41 suggesting inherent instability for this subset of metabolites (**Figure 2**). Evaluation of metabolite change
42 across chemical classes revealed that polar metabolites, including common amino acids, creatine,
43 hypoxanthine, uridine and carnitine among thousands of other metabolites changed minimally at RT
44 over the 7-day period (**Suppl Figure 2A**). Prior work has suggested that these molecules may be
45 susceptible to degradation over much longer periods of time at RT.³⁴ In contrast, we find lipophilic
46 molecules were more prone to fluctuation with RT storage over the 7-day period, with a steady increase
47 in number of measured metabolites over time, suggestive of oxidative conversion and/or breakdown of
48 metabolites into secondary products (**Suppl Figure 2B, 2C**). Overall, small polar bioactive molecules
49 revealed the greatest change at RT, consistent with their known susceptibility to non-enzymatic
50 oxidation (**Suppl Figure 2B**), similar to previous reports.¹⁸ Consistent with this observation, RT storage
51 without a desiccant pouch or an oxygen absorber exacerbated oxidation of small bioactive lipid
52 molecules (data not shown).

1 **Comparison of Analytes derived from DBS versus plasma**

2 To determine whether DBS introduces sample-matrix interactions that impact metabolite measures,
3 nontargeted LC-MS based metabolomics was performed on matched DBS and plasma samples.
4 Chemical network analysis was then performed to compare metabolites based on MS/MS spectral
5 similarities, with indexing of metabolites into three groups: (1) present in DBS only, (2) present in plasma
6 samples only, and (3) present in both DBS and plasma (**Figure 3**).^{28,35,36} The vast majority of metabolite
7 families observed in plasma samples were also observed in DBS samples, including phosphocholines,
8 phosphoethanolamines, phosphoserines, sphingomyelins, oxylipins, phosphoinositols, polyunsaturated
9 fatty acids, sterol and sterol-glucuronides, monosaccharides, bile acids, glutathione and glutathione-
10 conjugates, nucleotides, amino acids, porphyrins, and carnitines, as well as hundreds to thousands of
11 yet unidentified metabolites (**Figure 3**). A small subset of unknown metabolite families was uniquely
12 present in only plasma or only DBS samples (**Figure 3**), likely representing metabolites resulting from
13 clotting or enriched in red blood cells, respectively. Collectively, these results suggest that DBS
14 sampling enables capture and measure of diverse metabolites comparable to LC-MS analysis of
15 traditional plasma samples.
16

17 **CONCLUSION**

18 Dried blood spot sampling offers unique opportunities for facile and efficient collection and storage of
19 blood biosamples with subsequent measure of hundreds to thousands of metabolites across diverse
20 chemical classes. Importantly, DBS-based metabolomics was found to be highly robust with technical
21 variance comparable to that of traditional plasma-based LC-MS,^{10,28} despite additional technical
22 considerations related to puncture of blood spots and extraction of metabolites from the paper matrix.
23 In addition, DBS sampling enables measure of diverse metabolites, from polar small molecules to
24 nonpolar lipids, with comparability to metabolites assayed from traditional plasma samples using
25 nontargeted LC-MS approaches. Finally, metabolites in DBS appear relatively stable at RT, enabling
26 sampling and facile handling in resource-poor areas or remote point-of-care sites, prior to cold storage
27 and analysis in centralized facilities. DBS sampling has established utility in specific clinical contexts
28 such as newborn screening and given the observed applications for broad interrogation of the circulating
29 metabolome. Our data support the need for future investigation of DBS generated from finger stick as
30 a blood collection and storage strategy which may be of high utility in resource-limited areas as well as
31 in population- scale efforts aimed at relating metabolomics measures to indices of health and disease.
32

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40 **Author Contributions:** M.J., F.I., S.C., S.S., C.W., S.N. and J.D.W conceived the project and designed
41 experiments. C.W., J.D.W, and E.A., performed DBS and LC-MS experiments. S.S. and I.M. obtained
42 DBS samples. C.W., J.D.W, S.N. T.L. and M.J. analyzed and interpreted the data. C.W., S.N., J.D.W.,
43 F.I., and M.J. wrote and edited the manuscript.
44

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46

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1 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

2
3 **Figure 1. Non-targeted reversed-phase LC- Orbitrap MS analysis of DBS.** A. Schematic of dried
4 blood spot collection, processing and analysis. After blood is spotted on DBS, metabolites are extracted
5 from 3 mm punches taken from DBS and then analyzed by non-targeted MS. B. Optimization of
6 extraction procedures for **Polar metabolites** based on number of observed features and their
7 corresponding signal intensities. Optimization of organic extraction solvent (left panel), organic solvent
8 to water ratio (middle panel) and supernatant concentration (right panel). C. Schematic of DBS punch
9 location (P, peripheral punch; C, Center punch) and variation in spectral peak intensity with punch
10 location represented in a Venn diagram showing the number of features that vary by less than 2-fold by
11 location (center overlap), as well the features that vary more than 2-fold in the center (left) and peripheral
12 (right) locations. Data represents aggregated data on unique spectral peaks across all Polar, Bioactives
13 and Lipids metabolites. D. Comparison of intensity versus relative standard deviation (RSD) for all
14 spectral features across replicate samples (20% RSD indicated by dashed line). E. Dynamic linear
15 range and relative quantification of metabolites extracted from control CDC DBS cards with known
16 concentrations of target metabolites. Linearity plots for 3 representative metabolites (phenylalanine,
17 acylcarnitine, and succinylacetone) measured from CDC DBS cards are shown.
18

19 **Figure 2. Stability of DBS metabolites.** Fold Change (represented as \log_2 fold change) in measured
20 signal intensity for metabolites from DBS stored at room temperature over 7 days. The first and third
21 quartile of the \log_2 fold-change is represented by the lower and upper boundaries of the white bar in the
22 center of the violin plots, respectively. The median \log_2 fold-change is represented by the black line in
23 the white bar in the center of the violin plots. Wider sections of the violin plot represent higher frequency
24 of measures in the corresponding range of fold-change. Dashed red lines represent a 2-fold increase
25 or decrease compared to day 0.
26

27 **Figure 3. Chemical networking of metabolites from DBS and plasma.** LC-MS/MS data collected
28 from DBS and matched plasma samples were subjected to spectral chemical networking and clustered
29 according to MS/MS spectral similarity. Metabolites present in DBS only, plasma only, and both plasma
30 and DBS were denoted in red, yellow, and blue, respectively. Known metabolites include 1)
31 Phosphocholines, 2) Phosphoethanolamines, 3) Phosphoserines, 4) Sphingomyelins, 5) Oxylipins, 6)
32 Phosphoinositols, 7) Polyunsaturated fatty acids, 8) Sterol / Sterol-glucuronides, 9) Monosaccharides,
33 10) Bile acids, 11) Glutathione / Glutathione-conjugates, 12) Nucleotide phosphates, 13) Amino acids,
34 14) Porphyrins, and 15) Carnitines.
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1 **SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURE LEGENDS**

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3 **Supplemental Figure 1.** A. Effect of solvent choice (left panel), solvent dilution (middle panel), and
4 supernatant volume (right panel) on number of peaks observed and overall median intensity for small
5 polar lipids (Bioactives). B. Effect of solvent choice (left panel), solvent dilution (middle panel) and
6 supernatant dilution (right panel) on number of peaks observed and overall median intensity for large
7 hydrophilic lipid (Lipids). C. Composition of \log_2 (fold intensity) changes between center and periphery
8 spots across all 3 classes of metabolites.
9

10 **Supplemental Figure 2.** Fold Change (represented as \log_2 fold change) in measured signal intensity
11 for different chemical classes of metabolites extracted from DBS stored at room temperature over 7
12 days. The first and third quartile of the \log_2 fold-change is represented by the lower and upper
13 boundaries of the white bar in the center of the violin plots, respectively. The median \log_2 fold-change
14 is represented by the black line in the white bar in the center of the violin plots. Wider sections of the
15 violin plot represent higher frequency of measures in the corresponding range of fold-change. Dashed
16 red lines represent a 2 fold increase or decrease compared to day 0. Although a few analytes show a
17 large fold-change, more change is noted in lipophilic analytes as opposed to hydrophilic analytes (Polar
18 and Bioactives).
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1 **TABLES**2
3 **Table 1 – Relative Quantitation for Known Metabolites from DBS**4

Metabolite	Concentration Range ($\mu\text{Mol/L}$)	R²
Alanine	200 - 600	0.97
Arginine	100 - 300	0.99
Citrulline	25 - 250	0.99
Glycine	300 - 900	0.98
Leucine	100 - 500	0.99
Methionine	50 - 250	0.99
Ornithine	100 - 300	0.98
Phenylalanine	100 - 300	0.99
Succinylacetone	2.5 - 15	0.98
Tyrosine	200 - 600	0.99
Valine	150 - 500	0.99
C0 (Free Carnitine)	10 - 30	0.99
C2 (Acetylcarnitine)	10 - 30	0.99
C3 (Propionylcarnitine)	4 - 12	0.99
C3DC (Malonylcarnitine)	1.0 - 5.5	0.99
C4 (Butyrylcarnitine)	1.0 - 5.0	0.99
C4OH (Hydroxybutyrylcarnitine)	1.0 - 5.5	0.99
C5 (Isovalerylcarnitine)	0.5 - 3.0	0.99
C5DC (Glutarylcarnitine)	0.5 - 2.5	0.99
C5OH (Hydroxyisovalerylcarnitine)	0.5 - 3.0	0.99
C6 (Hexanoylcarnitine)	0.5 - 2.5	0.99
C8 (Octanoylcarnitine)	0.5 - 2.5	0.99
C10 (Decanoylcarnitine)	0.5 - 2.5	0.99
C12 (Dodecanoylcarnitine)	0.5 - 3.0	0.99
C14 (Myristoylcarnitine)	0.5 - 3.0	0.99
C16 (Palmitoylcarnitine)	4.0 - 12	0.99
C16OH (Hydroxypalmitoylcarnitine)	0.25 - 1.5	0.99
C18 (Stearoylcarnitine)	1.0 - 5.0	0.99
C18OH (Hydroxystearoylcarnitine)	0.25 - 1.5	0.99

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Figure 1

Figure 2

DBS and Plasma

DBS Only

Figure 3

Compound Name	Error (ppm)	MS2 Match Score
1,2-Dilauroyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphatidylcholine	5.0	0.95
1,5-Anhydro-sorbitol	0.1	0.96
10,11-Dihydro-10,11-dihydroxycarbamazepine	3.0	0.93
11,14,17-Eicosatrienoic acid	2.3	0.84
11-Nor-9-Carboxy-THC	0.6	0.92
12,13-EpOME	2.9	0.96
12-HETE	2.7	0.95
13-Docosenamide	1.8	0.88
13-HODE	0.4	0.98
13-Hydroxy-9Z,11E-octadecadienoic acid	0.3	0.98
14,15-EET	2.5	0.95
14-HDoHE	4.0	0.89
15-HETrE	2.6	0.98
15-Methylprostaglandin A2	4.3	0.91
16-HETE	2.4	0.97
17-Phenyltrior-13,14-dihydroprostaglandin A2	7.0	0.84
1-Methyladenosine	4.9	0.92
1-Methyl-histidine	0.0	0.89
1-Methylnicotinamide	3.0	0.96
1-Myristoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine	1.8	0.96
1-O-Hexadecyl-2-O-(2E-butenoyl)-sn-glyceryl-3-phosphochol	4.0	0.91
1-Oleoyl-alpha-lysophosphatidic acid	2.8	0.90
1-Palmitoyl-2-hydroxy-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine	0.1	0.99
2,3-Diphospho-glyceric acid	2.4	0.85
2,5-Dimethoxyphenol	2.3	0.84
20-HDoHE	6.3	0.84
2-Amino-1-phenylethanol	0.3	0.97
2'-Deoxyguanosine 5'-triphosphate	2.5	0.85
2-Hydroxy-2-methylbutyric acid	0.5	0.89
2'-Hydroxy-3,4,4'-trimethoxychalcone	2.6	0.92
2-Hydroxybutyric acid	1.2	0.91
2S-Amino-4E-octadecene-1,3S-diol	0.6	0.93
3-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)lactate	3.4	0.94
3,7-Dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavone	2.4	0.86
3-amino-Benzoic acid	2.3	0.80
3-beta-Hydroxy-5-cholenoic acid	0.2	0.88
3-Carboxy-4-methyl-5-propyl-2-furanpropanoic acid	3.1	0.89
3-Hydroxy-3'-methoxyflavone	3.0	0.91
3-Hydroxy-6-methoxyflavone	2.7	0.89
3-Hydroxybutyrylcarnitine	3.3	0.99
3-Hydroxyisovaleroylcarnitine	2.7	0.98
3-Hydroxyoleylcarnitine	0.6	0.92
3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenylglycol sulfate	0.7	0.90
3-Phenyllactic acid	1.8	0.81
4-Ethylbenzoic acid	8.4	0.81
4-Guanidinobutanoate	3.5	0.90

4-Hydroperoxy-2-nonenal	2.4	0.85
4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	0.1	0.82
4-Hydroxyhexenal	4.1	0.86
4-Hydroxy-proline	3.9	0.81
4-Ketopimelic acid	3.4	0.84
5,11,14-Eicosatrienoic acid	1.2	0.98
5,8,14-Eicosatrienoic acid	2.3	0.89
5-alpha-Androstan-17-beta-ol-3-one glucosiduronate	2.0	0.86
5-alpha-Androstandiol-glucuronic acid	1.4	0.84
5-Aminolevulinic acid	1.2	0.90
5-HETE	2.4	0.97
5-HETrE	1.6	0.93
5'-Methylthioadenosine	2.3	0.90
5-Oxo-proline	2.3	0.90
7-alpha-Hydroxy-3-oxo-4-cholestenoic acid	0.9	0.85
7-Oxcholesterol	1.1	0.95
8(9)-Dehydrocholesterol	0.7	0.81
8,9-Epoxyeicosa-14(Z)-enoic acid	0.7	0.98
8-HETE	1.3	0.92
9(10)-EpOME	2.1	0.90
9-HODE	3.2	0.88
9-HOTrE	0.5	0.84
9-HPODE	0.9	0.86
9-OxoODE	0.1	0.98
Acetyl-carnitine	1.9	0.93
Aconitic acid	0.3	0.95
Adenine	3.9	0.83
Adenosine 2'-monophosphate	4.1	0.91
Adenosine 5'-diphosphate	3.0	0.95
Adenosine 5'-diphosphoribose	0.2	0.88
Adenosine 5'-monophosphate	4.7	0.85
Adenosine 5'-triphosphate	3.2	0.93
Alanine	2.8	0.81
Alanyl-norleucine	1.4	0.80
alpha-Glucose 1,6-bisphosphate	2.4	0.98
Aminobenzoic acid	3.3	0.95
Amitriptyline	2.6	0.94
Androstan-3-ol-17-one 3-glucuronide	2.0	0.85
Arabinose	0.8	0.91
Arachidic acid	2.4	0.84
Arachidonic acid	2.3	0.94
Arginine	2.0	0.99
Asn-Ala	0.1	0.82
Asparagine	3.9	0.80
Aspartic acid	0.3	0.97
Benzoylecgonine	2.8	1.00
beta-Allose	0.2	0.84

beta-Hyodeoxycholic acid	0.3	0.93
Betaine	4.7	0.97
beta-Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide	0.9	0.90
Bilirubin	1.4	0.80
Biliverdin	1.2	0.92
Butyrylcarnitine	1.4	0.98
Caffeate	2.6	0.93
Canavanine	5.8	0.89
Carbamazepine	0.6	0.96
Carbamazepine 10,11-epoxide	2.3	0.95
Carnitine	0.4	0.87
Carnosine	3.2	0.90
Chenodeoxycholic acid	0.6	0.93
Cholic acid	1.7	0.95
Choline cation	2.1	0.86
cis-10,11-Dihydroxy-10,11-dihydrocarbamazepine	1.9	0.89
cis-5,8,11-Eicosatrienoic acid	0.3	0.98
Citrazinic acid	2.9	0.84
Citric acid	5.9	0.95
Citrulline	2.3	0.99
Cotinine	1.1	0.93
Creatine	1.8	1.00
Cytisine	3.7	0.83
Deoxycholic acid	3.7	0.97
D-erythro-C18-Sphingosine	2.4	0.91
D-erythro-N-stearoylsphingosine	0.1	0.94
D-erythro-Sphinganine	0.1	0.95
D-erythro-Sphingosine-1-phosphate	0.8	0.96
Desmethylcitalopram	1.0	0.92
Dihydrooorotate	3.0	0.88
Diphenylphosphate	0.2	0.90
Docosahexaenoyl PAF C-16	3.3	0.94
Ecgonine	2.6	0.99
Eicosapentaenoyl PAF C-16	4.9	0.94
Ergothioneine	1.8	0.99
ESTRIOL	2.3	0.89
Ethyl nitroacetate	4.1	0.87
Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid	2.9	1.00
Fructose	0.7	0.88
Fumarate	6.3	0.90
Galactose	0.7	0.88
Gibberellin A4	3.3	0.91
Gluconic acid	0.2	0.98
Glutamic acid	4.3	0.92
Glutamine	0.2	0.97
Glutathione, oxidized	0.0	0.96
Glyceric acid	3.3	0.94

Glycerophosphocholine	2.2	1.00
Glycocholic acid	0.5	0.85
Glycoursodeoxycholic acid	3.1	0.85
Guanine	3.0	0.89
Gulono-1,4-lactone	0.4	0.99
Hemin cation	0.3	0.97
Hexanoyl-carnitine	1.3	0.83
Hippuric acid	0.5	0.99
Histidine	4.0	0.89
Homoarginine	1.5	0.91
Hypotaurine	3.5	0.82
Hypoxanthine	0.3	0.99
Indole-3-lactic acid	0.3	0.95
Inosine 5'-phosphate	0.4	0.82
Isoallocholic acid	2.3	0.86
Isoleucine	2.1	0.95
Isovaleryl-carnitine	1.2	0.95
KDdiA-PC	0.2	0.86
Kynurenine	3.9	0.93
L-Arachidonoylcarnitine	0.6	0.93
Lenticin	1.1	0.90
Leucine	2.8	0.98
Linolenic acid	2.3	0.94
Linoleoylcarnitine	0.9	0.98
Lysine	2.7	0.84
Lyso-PAF C-18	2.4	0.96
Lyso-PC(16:0)	2.3	0.97
Lyso-PC(17:0)	1.4	0.97
Lyso-PC(18:0)	1.0	0.99
Lyso-PC(18:1)	3.5	0.97
Lyso-PC(18:3)	2.2	0.96
Lyso-PC(20:0)	2.5	0.96
Lyso-PC(22:0)	0.6	0.87
Lyso-PC(24:0)	3.9	0.88
Lyso-PC(O-18:0)	0.5	0.98
Lyso-PC(P-18:0)	0.6	0.93
Lyso-PE(16:0)	0.3	0.95
Lyso-PE(18:0)	3.0	0.98
Lyso-PE(18:1)	2.4	0.96
Lyso-PE(20:3)	3.7	0.96
Lyso-PE(20:4)	0.8	0.91
Malic acid	0.1	0.99
Maliomycin	0.1	0.99
Malonyl-carnitine	5.0	0.92
Melezitose	1.9	0.85
Meloxicam	0.9	0.90
Methionine	3.7	0.99

Methionine sulfoxide	3.5	0.88
Myo-Inositol	0.2	0.83
Myristoyl-carnitine	1.0	0.98
N,N-Dimethyl-arginine	2.0	0.92
N-Acetyl-beta-mannosamine	4.8	0.92
N-Acetyl-galactosamine 4-sulfate	1.3	0.84
N-Acetyl-galactosaminitol	1.8	0.86
N-Acetyl-glucosamine	3.3	0.95
N-Acetyl-glutamine	0.3	0.98
N-Acetylhistidine	3.1	0.93
N-Acetylmannosamine	7.8	0.90
N-Acetyl-methionine	0.1	0.95
NAD	4.8	0.90
N-Alpha-acetyl-lysine	2.5	0.87
N-Butylbenzenesulfonamide	2.4	0.93
N-epsilon-Acetyl-lysine	1.0	0.88
N-epsilon-trimethyl-lysine	3.4	0.96
Nicotinamide	9.0	0.99
N-Lauroyl-erythro-sphingosylphosphorylcholine	4.1	0.93
Octanoylcarnitine	0.6	0.87
Octopamine	6.1	0.88
Oleoyl-carnitine	1.2	0.99
OPPC	0.1	0.95
Ornithine	0.0	0.95
Orotic Acid	1.5	0.87
Oxcarbazepine	0.5	0.89
PA(34:1)	1.3	0.96
PA(34:2)	0.4	0.99
PA(36:2)	0.9	0.88
PAF C-16	0.8	0.94
Palmitoyl sphingomyelin	1.4	1.00
Palmitoylcarnitine	0.2	0.98
Pantothenic acid	1.6	0.94
PC(15:0)	0.6	0.97
PC(18:1)	1.4	0.98
PC(28:0)	0.4	0.97
PC(30:0)	3.2	0.96
PC(30:1)	2.4	0.90
PC(30:1)	4.9	0.86
PC(30:2)	3.1	0.91
PC(31:1)	3.0	0.90
PC(32:0)	1.7	0.95
PC(32:1)	2.0	0.98
PC(32:2)	4.4	0.96
PC(32:3)	2.9	0.86
PC(34:1)	3.0	0.95
PC(34:2)	2.1	0.98

PC(36:0)	3.3	0.93
PC(36:1)	5.2	0.94
PC(36:2)	1.8	0.98
PC(36:4)	0.1	0.97
PC(36:5)	0.9	0.95
PC(36:6)	3.2	0.95
PC(37:4)	4.9	0.89
PC(38:2)	3.9	0.89
PC(38:3)	5.5	0.94
PC(38:4)	3.9	0.86
PC(38:6)	3.4	0.93
PC(40:6)	1.0	0.98
PC(40:8)	7.2	0.93
PC(42:0)	2.4	0.83
PC(O-16:0/16:1)	3.2	0.85
PC(O-34:1)	7.8	0.95
PC(O-36:4)	5.9	0.96
PC(O-38:6)	6.1	0.92
PC(P-30:0)	3.3	0.91
PC(P-32:1)	3.3	0.86
PC(P-32:1)	3.1	0.83
PC(P-36:1)	3.6	0.97
PC(P-38:4)	0.6	0.96
PE(34:1)	1.1	0.95
PE(34:2)	0.9	0.91
PE(36:1)	0.7	0.80
PE(36:2)	0.9	0.89
PE(36:4)	5.5	0.83
PE(38:4)	1.0	0.82
PE(40:6)	2.0	0.81
PE(P-38:4)	2.0	0.85
PG(34:1)	0.6	0.86
Phe-Leu	2.1	0.82
Phenylacetyl-glutamine	1.4	0.98
Phenylalanine	2.6	1.00
Phosphocholine	2.8	0.87
Phosphoglyceric acid	5.8	0.98
p-Hydroxyphenyllactic acid	0.1	0.97
PI(16:0)	8.4	0.87
PI(18:1)	6.7	0.92
PI(38:4)	1.0	0.88
Pipecolic acid	2.5	0.96
Pipecolinic acid	1.3	0.95
Propionylcarnitine	2.2	0.99
Prostaglandin A3	4.4	0.83
Prostaglandin F2a	2.3	0.82
Protoporphyrin IX	0.2	0.94

PS(36:1)	1.2	0.95
PS(36:2)	1.0	0.98
PS(38:4)	0.2	0.99
PS(40:6)	0.9	0.93
Psicose	2.8	0.92
p-Tolyl Sulfate	5.5	0.95
Quinic acid	7.0	0.90
Salicylaldehyde	0.5	0.87
Ser-Ile	1.7	0.85
Serine	1.0	0.90
Ser-Phe	2.5	0.96
Shikimic acid	7.2	0.86
SM(d16:1/23:0)	2.3	0.85
SM(d17:1/24:1)	2.6	0.87
SM(d18:0/16:0)	2.5	0.89
SM(d18:1/18:0)	1.7	0.99
SM(d18:1/18:1)	0.6	0.98
SM(d18:1/21:0)	6.2	0.85
SM(d18:1/23:0)	6.7	0.84
SM(d18:1/24:1)	2.3	0.89
SM(d18:2/18:0)	2.4	0.83
SM(d18:2/20:0)	4.0	0.91
SM(d18:2/23:0)	2.6	0.85
SM(d18:2/24:0)	2.5	0.85
S-Methyl-cysteine	0.4	0.94
Sorbitol	0.3	0.96
Sorbose	0.1	0.82
Sorbosonic acid	1.9	0.83
Stachydrine	1.8	0.99
Stearoyl ethanolamide	0.6	0.91
Stearoyl-carnitine	0.4	0.98
Tagatose	0.2	0.81
Taurine	0.2	1.00
Tetranor-PGAM	3.3	0.84
Threonic acid	0.3	0.96
Threonine	5.2	0.99
Thr-Leu	1.7	0.94
Trans-3'-Hydroxycotinine	1.3	0.95
Trans-4-hydroxyproline	3.0	0.81
Trans-cyclohexane-1,2-diol	2.4	0.90
Trigonelline	3.6	0.90
Tropic acid	2.3	0.80
Tryptophan	2.1	0.95
Tyr-His	2.4	0.82
Tyrosine	6.2	0.97
Ureidosuccinic acid	5.5	0.92
Uric acid	0.5	1.00

Uridine 5'-diphosphogalactose	0.5	0.83
Ursocholic acid	3.1	0.97
Valerylcarnitine	1.6	0.85
Valine	3.9	0.97
Xylose	0.8	0.91

